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CET AI Mentor: AI-Based College Selection and Guidance System Using Machine Learning

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ABSTRACT

Choosing the right college after the CET becomes a difficult task for several candidates owing to a lot of factors such as availability of numerous colleges, different cut-off marks, and category wise rules. Candidates often become confused and have to seek manual assistance from others to get their doubts cleared and do things correctly.

In order to deal with such situations, this project attempts to develop the CET AI Mentor, a college prediction application that uses machine learning techniques to help students identify colleges. The system helps identify suitable colleges considering factors like CET score, rank, and category based on admission data from the past.

All that users need to do is enter their necessary data, after which the system will provide a list of colleges where chances of getting admitted are very high.

Overall, this method proves to be faster, simpler, and more efficient than traditional ones used by other candidates.

Keywords :- *CET, analyze past data, CET AI Mentor, reduces confusion, predictive analytics, getting admission, assumptions, domain, predictive analytics*

1. Introduction

In today's time, technology is improving every field, including education. One of the most important decisions for students is choosing the right college after entrance exams. In India, exams like CET play a major role in deciding college admissions, especially for engineering and other professional courses.

After getting their CET results, students often face confusion while selecting colleges. There are many options available, and students need to consider factors like cutoff marks, rank, category, branch, and college reputation. Checking all this information manually is time-consuming and sometimes difficult to understand. Because of this, many students depend on others' advice or guesswork, which may not always be correct.

With the help of modern technology, this problem can be solved more easily. Machine learning is one such technology that can analyze past data and make predictions. It is already used in many areas and is now becoming useful in education as well. It helps in reducing manual effort and gives faster results.

In this project, we developed a system called CET AI Mentor, which helps students predict suitable colleges based on their CET score and other details. The system uses previous years' admission data like cutoff marks and ranks to understand patterns and provide suggestions. This makes the process easier compared to manually checking multiple sources.

The system is simple to use. Students just need to enter their details, and it shows a list of colleges where they have a good chance of getting admission. This saves time and reduces confusion. It also helps students make better decisions based on data instead of assumptions.

Overall, this system shows how machine learning can be used to solve real problems

in education. It makes the college selection process easier, faster, and more reliable for students.

2. Literature Review

In recent years, the use of machine learning and data mining in the education sector has increased a lot. Many researchers have started working on systems that can help in predicting student performance, college admissions, and placement outcomes. These technologies are mainly used to reduce manual effort and improve the accuracy of decision-making.

Several studies have focused on developing automated college prediction systems using machine learning. These systems analyze student-related data such as marks, ranks, and other academic details to suggest suitable colleges. It has been observed that machine learning models can handle large amounts of data and provide better predictions compared to traditional methods. Among different algorithms, the Naïve Bayes classifier is commonly used because it is simple, fast, and gives good results in classification problems. It has shown satisfactory accuracy in predicting college admissions based on student input.

Apart from classification algorithms, some researchers have also used clustering techniques like K-Means. In this approach, students are grouped based on similarities such as academic performance, background, and preferences. This grouping helps in identifying patterns in the data and improves the prediction process. It is especially useful when the dataset is large and needs to be organized into meaningful groups.

There are also studies that use advanced techniques like ensemble learning methods. Algorithms such as Random Forest and Gradient Boosting combine multiple models to improve overall performance. These methods are known to give more

accurate results compared to single models because they reduce errors and improve prediction quality. In many cases, Random Forest has performed better than other algorithms due to its ability to handle complex data and avoid overfitting.

Another important concept used in this field is predictive analytics. It involves using past data to understand future outcomes. In the education domain, predictive analytics helps in forecasting student results, admission chances, and other academic decisions. By analyzing historical data, these systems can give useful suggestions and help students plan their future in a better way.

Even though many systems have been developed, some limitations still exist. A number of existing approaches depend on manual processes or use limited datasets, which can affect the accuracy of predictions. Also, some systems are not very user-friendly, making it difficult for students to use them effectively. Because of this, there is still a need for better systems that are simple, accurate, and easy to use.

The proposed system in this project tries to overcome these problems. It combines machine learning algorithms with a simple and user-friendly interface. The model is trained using historical CET data, which helps in understanding admission trends. Based on the user's input, the system provides predictions about suitable colleges in a quick and efficient way.

Overall, the studies in this area show that machine learning is very useful in solving problems related to education. It helps in improving accuracy, saving time, and making better decisions. The CET AI Mentor system is developed based on these ideas and aims to provide a more practical and helpful solution for students during the college selection process.

3. Problem Statement

After appearing for CET, many students find it difficult to decide which college to choose for admission. The situation becomes confusing because there are many factors involved at the same time, such as cutoff marks, rank, category, branch preference, and seat availability. On top of that, students have to check previous year cutoff lists and admission data, which can be overwhelming and not always easy to understand.

Usually, students depend on manual ways like searching different websites, comparing information on their own, or asking friends, seniors, or consultants for advice. While this may help to some extent, it is not always accurate. Sometimes the information is incomplete or outdated, and students end up making decisions based on assumptions. This can lead to choosing a college that may not match their score or interest, which can affect their future.

Another issue is that there is no proper system that can quickly give accurate predictions based on student details. Most existing methods either take a lot of time or do not give reliable results. Because of this, students often feel unsure during the admission process and lack confidence in their decisions.

Looking at these problems, there is a need for a simple and effective solution that can reduce confusion and save time. A system that can use past admission data and give clear suggestions would be very helpful. It should allow students to understand their chances of getting admission into different colleges based on their CET score, after CET. Many students struggle to understand cutoff data and often feel confused while choosing colleges, so this system tries to simplify that process using machine learning.

In this system, students enter their details like CET score, rank, category, and preferred branch. After that, the system processes this input using a model trained on previous admission data. By looking at past cutoff trends and allotment records, it predicts a list of colleges where the chances of admission are higher. Instead of checking everything manually, students can get results quickly in one place.

The system is designed in a simple way so that it can be used easily without any technical knowledge. It reduces the need to depend on multiple websites or outside advice. At the same time, since the predictions are based on actual data, the results are more reliable than guesswork.

From a technical point of view, machine learning algorithms such as Naïve Bayes are used to make predictions. The system can also be improved over time by updating it with new admission data, which helps in making the results more accurate.

Overall, this system provides a practical solution by saving time, reducing confusion, and helping students make better decisions about their college selection, rank, and category in an easy way.

To solve this problem, this project proposes a machine learning-based system called **CET AI Mentor**. The system is designed to predict suitable colleges for students and make the admission process easier, faster, and more reliable.

4. Proposed System

The CET AI Mentor system is proposed to make the college selection process easier for students

5. System Architecture

The system architecture of CET AI Mentor shows how the whole system works step by step to give college predictions to students. The main idea behind this design is to keep the process simple, understandable, and

useful. Instead of making it complex, the system is divided into a few basic parts, and each part has its own role. All these components are connected and work together to give the final result.

At the beginning, the student interacts with the system through a simple interface. The user interface is designed in such a way that even a non-technical student can easily use it without confusion. Here, the student enters details like CET score, rank, category, and preferred branch. The focus is to collect correct input without making the process complicated.

5.1) User Interface (UI): This is the first part of the system where students provide their details. It is kept simple and clear so that users do not face any difficulty while entering information.

After the input is given, the data does not go directly to the prediction model. It first passes through a processing stage. In real-world situations, input data may not always be clean or properly formatted. So, this step helps in organizing and preparing the data.

5.2) Data Processing Module: In this stage, the system checks the input, removes small errors if present, and converts the data into a format that the machine learning model can understand. This step improves the overall performance of the system.

Another important part of the architecture is the dataset. The system depends on past admission records to make predictions. This data includes cutoff marks, ranks, categories, and college allotment details from previous years. Instead of depending on guesswork, the system uses this real data to learn patterns.

5.3) Dataset(Historical Data): This contains previous year admission information. It helps the system understand how admissions were done earlier and

plays a key role in training the model.

The main working of the system happens in the machine learning model. This is the core part where predictions are made. The model is trained using the dataset so that it can learn relationships between input values and output results. When a new user enters their details, the model compares it with the learned data and predicts suitable colleges.

5.4) Machine Learning

Model: This is the main component where prediction takes place. Algorithms like Naïve Bayes are used because they are simple and effective for this type of classification problem.

Once the prediction is done, the system shows the result to the user. The output is kept simple and easy to understand. Instead of showing complex data, the system provides a list of colleges where the student has a higher chance of getting admission.

5.5) Output Module:

This part displays the final result in the form of predicted colleges. It helps students quickly understand their options.

If we look at the complete working, it follows a simple flow. The student enters details, the system processes the data, the model analyzes it using past records, and finally, the output is generated. All these steps are connected and happen in a short time.

- Working Flow of the System:
 1. Student enters CET details
 2. Data is processed and prepared
 3. Model analyzes data using dataset
 4. Prediction is generated
 5. Results are displayed to the user

One good thing about this architecture is that it can be improved over time. As new data becomes available, it can be added to the system, which helps in increasing accuracy. Also, the design is simple, so it is easy to maintain and update.

In conclusion, the system architecture of CET AI Mentor is designed in a simple and practical way. It focuses on solving the real problem faced by students during college selection. By combining user input, data processing, and machine learning, the system provides useful and reliable predictions, making the admission process easier and less confusing.

6. Technologies Used

6.1 Frontend Technology

For the frontend part, React.js is used. It helps in creating a simple and interactive user interface. Students can easily enter their details like CET score, rank, category, and branch without any confusion. React also makes the system faster and gives a smooth user experience while using the application.

6.2 Backend Technology

For backend development, Node.js is used. It handles all the server-side work and manages the communication between frontend and machine learning model. Whenever a user enters data, Node.js processes the request and sends it to the model, then returns the result. It helps in

making the system fast and responsive.

6.3 Machine Learning Technology

For implementing machine learning, Python is used. A library called Scikit-learn is used to build the prediction model. In this project, the Naïve Bayes algorithm is used because it is simple and works well for prediction problems. The model uses past CET data to understand patterns and predict suitable colleges based on user input.

6.4 Database Technology

MySQL is used as the database in this system. It stores all important data like previous year cutoff marks, ranks, and college details. This data is used by the system while making predictions. It helps in keeping the data organized and easy to access whenever required.

6.5 Dataset Handling using Excel (CSV) and Python

In this project, the dataset is prepared using Excel and saved in CSV format. It contains details like CET score/rank, category, college name, branch, and cutoff marks.

The CSV file is then used in Python, where it is loaded using libraries like pandas. The data is checked and used to train the machine learning model.

The model learns from past data and, based on user input, predicts suitable colleges.

In simple terms: Excel is used to store data, CSV is used to connect data, and Python is used for prediction.

6.6 Tools and Platform

Some additional tools are also used during development:

VS Code is used for writing and managing code Postman is used for testing APIs

Git is used for version control and tracking project changes

7. Implementation Details

The implementation of the CET AI Mentor system is done step by step by combining different parts of the system. The main focus while developing this project was to keep it simple and working properly, so that it can give useful college predictions based on the student's input. Instead of making it too complex, the system is designed in a practical way so that it is easy to understand and use.

First, the dataset is collected from previous CET admission records. This data includes details like marks, rank, category, cutoff, and college names. Since the system depends on this data, it is important to prepare it properly. After collecting the data, it is cleaned and arranged. Some values may be missing or not useful, so those are handled before using the data for training.

- **Data Collection & Preparation:** Past CET data is collected and cleaned so that it can be used correctly for building the model.

After preparing the data, the next step is building the machine learning model. In this project, a simple algorithm like Naïve Bayes is used because it works well for prediction problems. The model is trained

using the dataset so that it can learn patterns from past admission data. Once training is done, the model is tested using some sample inputs to check if the output is correct.

- **Model Training:**

The model is trained using past data so that it can understand how college allotment works.

Then, the model is connected to the backend. Here, Node.js is used to handle the communication between the frontend and the model. When a student enters their details, the backend receives that data and sends it to the model. After prediction, the result is sent back to the frontend.

- **Backend Integration:** It connects different parts of the system and makes sure the data flows properly.

At the same time, the frontend is developed using React.js. It is designed in a simple way so that students can easily enter their details. The interface shows input fields and also displays the result clearly. The aim is to make it user-friendly so that anyone can use it without confusion.

- **Frontend Development:** Provides a simple and clear interface for entering data and viewing results.

For storing the data, MySQL is used. It keeps all the required information like previous admission data and other details. This helps in managing the data properly and also supports the model during prediction.

- **Database Management:** Stores data in an organized way so that it can be easily accessed when needed.

Finally, testing is done to check whether the system is working correctly. Different inputs are given to see if the predictions are accurate. If any errors are found, they are

corrected to improve the system.

- **System Testing:**
Ensures that the system gives correct output and works without issues.

Overall, the implementation includes data preparation, model building, integration, and testing. All these steps are connected and help in creating a working system. The final system is simple, easy to use, and helps students in choosing the right college based on their CET performance.

8. Results and Discussion

The CET AI Mentor system was tested using different sample inputs to understand how well it works in predicting suitable colleges. The main idea behind testing was to check whether the system can give useful and practical suggestions based on CET score, rank, and category. Along with checking technical output, attention was also

given to how easy the system feels for a normal student to use.

During testing, various input values were given and the results were compared with previous years' admission data. It was noticed that in many cases, the colleges suggested by the system were quite close to actual cutoff trends. The results were not exactly the same every time, but they were mostly in a reasonable range. This shows that the model is able to understand patterns from past data and use them in prediction.

- **Prediction Accuracy:** The system gives fairly accurate results based on available historical data and user input, though it may vary slightly in some cases.

Another thing that was observed is the speed of the system. After entering the details, the result is shown quickly without much delay. Compared to manual checking, where students go through multiple websites and data, this process is much faster and more convenient.

- **Performance:**
The system responds quickly and saves time during the college selection process.

From a user point of view, the system is easy to handle. The interface is simple, and there is no need for technical knowledge to use it. Students can enter their details without confusion, and the output is shown in a clear format, which makes it easier to understand.

- **User Experience:**
The system is simple and user-friendly, which makes it suitable for all types of users.

At the same time, a few limitations were noticed. Since the system depends on past data, its accuracy is affected by how good and updated the dataset is. If the data is limited or outdated, the predictions may not be fully accurate. Also, the system does not consider sudden changes like new rules or unexpected cutoff variations.

- **Limitations:**
The system depends on historical data, so any sudden changes in admission trends may affect the results.

Even with these limitations, the overall working of the system is quite satisfactory. It reduces the effort required by students to manually check data and gives them a general idea of which colleges they can expect. It works more like a guide rather than giving exact final results, which is still helpful during decision-making.

- **Overall Outcome:**
The system performs well and helps students make better decisions with less confusion.

In the end, it can be said that the CET AI Mentor system works in a useful way for predicting colleges. It saves time, simplifies the process, and gives students a clearer understanding of their chances. With more data and some improvements,

the system can become even more accurate and reliable in the future.

9. Advantages

1. Saves Time:

One of the biggest advantages is that it saves time. Students don't need to check multiple websites or go through long cutoff lists. They can simply enter their details and get results quickly.

2. Data-Based Prediction: The system gives suggestions based on previous admission data, so it is more reliable than guessing. It may not be 100% exact, but it still gives a good and practical idea.

3. User-Friendly:

The system is simple to use, and any student can easily understand it. There is no need for technical knowledge, and the interface is clear and easy.

4. Reduces Confusion:

Many students feel confused after CET about which college they might get. This system helps by giving a list of possible colleges, which makes decision-making easier.

5. Fast Processing:

The system works quickly. Once the details are entered, the result is shown within seconds, which is helpful during the admission process.

6. Updatable System:

Another good point is that the system can be improved over time. New admission data can be added, which helps in increasing accuracy.

7. Helpful Guidance:

Overall, the system acts like a guide. It doesn't give exact results every time, but it helps students understand their chances and make better choices.

Limitations

1. The system mainly depends on past admission data, so its accuracy depends on

10. Future Scope

1. In future, the system can be

improved by adding more updated admission data so that results become more accurate.

2. More details like student choice, location, fees, and college rating can be added to give better suggestions.

3. Better machine learning methods can be used to improve prediction quality.

4. This system can be made into a mobile app so students can use it easily on their phones.

5. Real-time updates like latest cutoff marks and admission news can be added.

6. A college comparison feature can be added so students can easily compare options.

7. The system can also support other entrance exams apart from CET.

8. A chatbot can be added to help students and answer their questions quickly.

9. The design of the system can be made more simple and attractive for user how updated and correct that data is.

2. If the dataset is old or incomplete, the predictions may not be fully accurate.

3. The system does not give exact results every time, as cutoff marks can change every year.

4. It only provides a general idea of possible colleges, not guaranteed admission results.

5. The system considers basic inputs like score, rank, and category, but does not include other factors like personal preferences or special cases.

6. Sudden changes in cutoff trends may not be handled properly since the model is based on past data.

7. If the data is not properly maintained, it can affect the performance of the system.

8. The system needs regular updates with new data, otherwise its accuracy may decrease over time.

9. It requires an internet connection to use, which may not always be available.

10. The system should be used as a

guiding tool, not as a final decision-maker.

11. Conclusion

In this project, we developed a system called CET AI Mentor to help students during the college selection process after CET. Many students face confusion because there are many colleges, different cutoff marks, and category rules. So, we tried to solve this problem using machine learning.

The system takes input like CET score, rank, and category, and based on previous year data, it suggests colleges where the student may have a good chance of getting admission. This makes the process easier compared to checking everything manually.

While working on this project, we understood how machine learning can be used in real-life problems. The system is simple and easy to use, so any student can use it without much difficulty. It also saves time and gives a basic idea about possible colleges.

There are some limitations, like the system depends on past data and cannot give 100% accurate results. But still, it works as a helpful guide for students.

In future, the system can be improved by adding more updated data and new features. Overall, this project was a good learning experience for us and shows how technology can help students in making better decisions.

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